

New records of intensive blooms of *Alexandrium minutum* (Dinophyceae) in the Jonian Sea, Italy

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Abstract

In Italy *Alexandrium minutum* is recurrently found at low concentrations in mussel farming areas, such as the Western Adriatic and the Sardinia coasts; mussels positive to PSP toxins have occasionally been detected but rarely exceeded the legal limit for commercial sale. Conversely, in South Italy, the Sicilian coast represents a hot spot of *A. minutum* blooms, repeatedly occurring in high densities. This study shows the presence of extensive blooms detected for the first time on the Jonian coast of Calabria at Roccella Jonica; the first bloom occurred in 2018, followed by a larger event in 2020. Both blooms occurred in March in the harbour dockyard, an area not monitored for toxic algae due to the absence of mussel farms. The blooms caused a yellow/brown water discoloration, but no PSP symptoms were reported. In order to understand if these blooms can cause harmful consequences, five *Alexandrium* strains were isolated from the 2018 event for molecular identification at the species level and analysis of the toxin content and profile. All strains were confirmed to belong to the *A. minutum* group and produce PSP toxins, with four out of five clones displaying higher toxin levels. The toxin profile displayed slight differences among strains, however, GTX 1,4 were the prevalent analogues, as previously observed in the Mediterranean region. Despite *A. minutum* blooms being rare events historically, intensive toxic blooms are increasing, especially on the South Italian coasts. This poses some concerns and highlights the need for better monitoring and management of the new identified spot and of nearby areas.

Keywords: *Alexandrium minutum*, harmful blooms, marine biotoxins, PSP toxins

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Introduction

Alexandrium minutum Halim, 1960 is a globally distributed dinoflagellate known to produce paralytic shellfish toxins, a family of compounds causing paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) in humans. The presence of this species is carefully monitored, thus there is a substantial database to evidence that its blooms are expanding to places where they were not previously observed.

In Europe, *A. minutum* blooms have occurred at different locations, especially in Northern coastal areas (Lewis *et al.*, 2018), but in the Southern Mediterranean region, recurrent blooms have been reported only from few places, in particular on the Catalan coast of Spain (Vila *et al.*, 2005) and, in Italy, in Sardinia (Bazzoni *et al.*, 2020) and in both the Tyrrhenian and Jonian coast of Sicily (Vila *et al.*, 2005; Costa *et al.*, 2021). These blooms usually occur in places characterized by sheltered and stratified waters, with inputs from rivers (Giacobbe *et al.*, 1995; Vila *et al.*, 2005). In different areas, such as the Western Adriatic Sea, *A. minutum* cells are detected every year, especially during spring, in numbers rarely exceeding 4,000 cells L⁻¹ and, even in the presence of higher concentrations, mussels contaminated by PSP toxins have rarely been detected (personal observations). In contrast, on the Sardinian coast (Tyrrhenian Sea), mussels positive to PSP toxins were found since 2002, although not continuously, despite the occurrence of low cell numbers. For example, in 2015, mussels were positive to PSP toxins although only 800 cells L⁻¹ were counted (Bazzoni *et al.*, 2016). It is thus possible to conclude that in Italy, with the exception of Sicily, *A. minutum* blooms can be considered rare events and, accordingly,

episodes of PSP levels exceeding the legal limit for mussel sales have occurred only on few occasions (in the Adriatic Sea, Sardinia and Sicily). The present study is aimed at reporting the occurrence, for the first time, of extensive blooms of *A. minutum* on the Jonian coast of Calabria (Roccella Jonica, province of Reggio Calabria; Fig. 1); results of a study aimed at species confirmation and toxicity evaluation are shown.

Fig. 1. Roccella Jonica geographic position.

Material and Methods

Seawater sampling

On March 2018 and 2020, water discoloration was noticed by eye; in both years 1 L of seawater was taken with a bottle in the bloom area for preliminary observations, then used for microscope cell identification and counting. An aliquot of the 2018 sample was utilized for cell isolation and culture set up.

Cell cultures

Single cells were isolated under the microscope through glass capillary tube

methods, the cells were allowed to divide in a 24-well plate in f/20 medium and after two weeks five *Alexandrium* spp. strains (C21I, C42I, C53I, C1D and C5D) could successfully be cultured in f/4 medium (f/20 and f/4 were made from Guillard f/2 modified in terms of N and P levels that were both 10- and 2-fold diluted, respectively).

Biovolume measurement

The cell volume of each strain was determined by measuring at least 60 cells in the stationary phase of growth under a light microscope. Cells were considered spherical according to Edler (1979).

DNA extraction and sequencing

Cultures in the exponential growth phase were collected for DNA isolation and analysis. Genomic DNA was extracted using the DNeasy Plant Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), the ITS - 5.8S region of the rDNA was then amplified (Fig. 3) and sequenced using the universal primer ITSA and ITSB (Adachi *et al.*, 1994).

Toxin analysis

Two liter cultures of each strain were collected by centrifugation and used for toxin analysis performed by means of Liquid Chromatography with Fluorescence Detection (LC-FLD) after derivatization in accordance with AOAC Official Method 2005.06.

Results and Discussion

Events and organism

At Roccella Jonica, the first water discoloration event occurred in March 2018, followed by a second one in the same month of 2020, the latter lasting until the middle of September. They both occurred in the harbour dockyard

where the water appeared intensely yellow/brown coloured from nearly 15 cm from the surface (Fig. 2). Observations under the light microscope pointed to the presence of an *A. minutum* bloom with cell numbers of 79×10^6 cells L^{-1} and 261×10^6 cells L^{-1} , in 2018 and 2020, respectively.

Fig. 2. Bloom of *A. minutum* in the field in 2020 (a) and under the light microscope (b); single cell, mean cell diameter of $20.81 \pm 1.42 \mu m$ (c).

The area is not monitored for toxic algae due to the absence of mussel farms, and during the bloom no one suffered from PSP symptoms. However, a correct identification and evaluation of toxins was undertaken at the first bloom appearance.

The five strains isolated from the 2018 field samples underwent molecular identification. The amplified ITS - 5.8S rDNA was about 550 bp (Fig. 3). All the clone sequences were confirmed to belong to the Mediterranean *A. minutum* species based on 100% rDNA gene sequence similarity using BLAST.

Fig. 3. Amplification of ITS – 5.8S rDNA region of *Alexandrium* spp. C21I, C42I, C53I, C1D and C5D strains. M: 100-bp ladder marker; CNT+: positive control; CNT-: negative control.

All the newly isolated algal strains were determined to be PSP toxin-producers and their toxin profiles were similar (Table 1): GTX 1,4 were the most prevalent analogues (72 - 100%), as previously observed in other strains from the Mediterranean area, whereas minor toxins slightly differed among strains.

Table 1. Toxin profile of the investigated strains.

Strain ID	GTX 2,3	C1,2	GTX 1,4 %	NEO
C53I		27.51	72.49	
C1D			100.00	
C5D	4.62		94.03	1.35
C21I		5.69	94.31	
C42I	4.13	2.84	90.97	2.06

Toxicity levels displayed higher variability but, generally, all the strains appeared to contain a total toxin content in the range of few fg cell⁻¹, with a maximum value of 23.71 fg cell⁻¹ (Table 2). These values are in the range of those measured in different strains from the Adriatic Sea (Perini *et al.*, 2014) and also in strains from other geographical zones (Nascimento *et al.*, 2005), however,

are very low compared to a strain previously analyzed from the Gulf of Trieste (Northern Adriatic Sea) which contained 964 fg cell⁻¹ of total saxitoxins (recalculated from Beani *et al.*, 2000). This difference led us to compare the biovolume of the various strains, all measured in the stationary phase, which resulted in being the same range: the strains from Roccella Jonica had a mean biovolume of 4,606 ± 510 μm³ and the one from the Gulf of Trieste of 6,347 ± 1577 μm³; the latter is slightly higher and accounted for a toxin content, on a biovolume-base, which is 31-fold higher than that of the most toxic strain isolated in Roccella Jonica (0.1519 and 0.0049 fg SXTs fL⁻¹ for Trieste and C5D strain, respectively).

Table 2. Toxicity of the investigated algal strains

Strain ID	Toxin content (fg cell ⁻¹)	Toxicity (fg SXTeq cell ⁻¹)
C53I	1.23	1.21
C1D	7.32	8.28
C5D	23.71	26.60
C21I	4.71	5.05
C42I	9.58	10.50

The reported blooms demonstrate that Roccella Jonica (Calabria Region) may be considered among the Italian Jonian areas which are affected by recurring PSP toxic *A. minutum* blooms, in addition to the Siracusa area (Sicily Region) where the blooms have occurred since 2000 (Vila *et al.*, 2005; Penna *et al.*, 2015; Costa *et al.*, 2019). Blooms detected in Roccella Jonica once more confirm the preference of *A. minutum* for sheltered areas and early spring months, as it was reported for blooms occurring in different areas of South Italy.

The molecular characterization suggests that this population belongs to the Jonian cluster of *A. minutum* in the Mediterranean Sea (Casabianca *et al.*, 2012). In regards to the toxic profile, the Jonic strains belong to cluster 1, which is the one spread throughout Europe, Australia, Taiwan and Malaysia (Lewis *et al.*, 2018). The new isolated strains do not appear highly toxic, however our results confirm the high variability of the toxic potency among strains of similar geographic origin. In view of *A. minutum*'s rapid growth and capacity to reach high cell abundance, its blooms with relatively low toxin per cell but many cells represent a significant source of PSP toxins to the environment.

These results highlight that it is worth increasing the monitoring effort in Roccella Jonica and to perform further investigations on the conditions triggering the blooms.

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